

Charge from an electron-muon-tau-centered point of view versus charge from an down-strange-bottom-centered point of view

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Abstract

If we do a 'Gedanken Experiment' of first principles, when we would meet someone and wanted to explain them elementary particle charge as simple as possible. The person would likely wonder why we assume the electron charge to be the fundamental unit of charge? Why do we? Wouldn't it be nice to explore the methods possible. If we say our current view is like the ancient view where the earth was in the center of the solar system, the geocentric model. We now know it's a heliocentric model, where the sun is in the center of our solar system.

We now have an electron centered point of view! (or electron-muon-tau, because they all have the same charge)

But which view makes the most sense? If we go through the up-charme-top-centered view we also obtain fractional charges.

But if we look at the down-strange-bottom-centered view we obtain only integer charges, i.e. whole charges! That turns our entire world view on its head, of course, but seems to give more meaning. It is the most effective way for our hypothetical friend to hold whole number charges in mind than charge fractions consisting of two whole numbers each. Not assuming anybody in the physics department could not manage that, but less is more efficient.

Charge from an electron-muon-tau-centered point of view

particle	charge
up-quark	$(2/3)$
down-quark	$(-1/3)$
charm-quark	$(2/3)$
strange-quark	$(-1/3)$
top-quark	$(2/3)$
bottom-quark	$(-1/3)$
electron	-1
muon	-1
tau	-1
e. neutino	0
m. neutrino	0
t. neutrino	0
photon	0
z-boson	0
w-boson	± 1
gluon	0
higgs	0

Focusing on lepton (not their respective neutrinos) centered charge we obtain fractional charges widely used in physics.

Charge from an down-strange-bottom-centered point of view

particle	charge
up-quark	(-2)
down-quark	1
charm-quark	(-2)
strange-quark	1
top-quark	(-2)
bottom-quark	1
electron	3
muon	3
tau	3
e. neutrino	0
m. neutrino	0
t. neutrino	0
photon	0
z-boson	0
w-boson	± 3
gluon	0
higgs	0

Focusing on d-s-b-centered charge we obtain whole integer charges very useful for providing new insights for a symmetry of triplets. The proton becomes up+up+down= $(-2)+(-2)+1=-2-2+1=-4+1=-3$ and the electron charge is opposite of that, of course, being 3. The Neutron charge becomes up+down+down= $(-2)+1+1=0$, being neutral. But in this way all particles and nucleons get integer charges.

Source Of Charge Values

(<https://i.sstatic.net/TDjRZ.png>, u.d.)

(physics stack exchange, u.d.),

URL: <https://physics.stackexchange.com/questions/255578/how-do-particles-get-their-charge>